

EFFECT OF CURING AGENTS IN DIFFERENT MOLECULAR STRUCTURE ON EPOXY RESIN BASED SOLID ELECTROLYTE FOR STRUCTURAL COMPOSITE BATTERY APPLICATION

Jaehoon Choi¹, Russell J. Varley¹, Salwan Al-Assafi², Bronwyn Fox³ and Minoos Naebe^{1*}

¹ Carbon Nexus at the Institute for Frontier Materials (IFM), Deakin University, Waurn Ponds, VIC, 3216, Australia ² Quickstep Holdings Limited Building LA, Deakin University, 75 Pigdons Road, Waurn Ponds, VIC, 3216, Australia ³ Faculty of Science, Engineering and Technology, Swinburne University of Technology, Hawthorn, Victoria, 3122, Australia

Keywords: Resin and Polymer, Polymer Matrix Materials, Composite Structures, Automotive

ABSTRACT

A systematic study of the impact of curing agents in different molecular structure for epoxy resin solid polyelectrolyte (SPE) is presented. The SPE is based on poly (ethylene glycol) diglycidyl ether (PEGDGE), which includes ethylene oxide (EO) on the polymer backbone. The amine-based curing agents in different molecular structure (aliphatic, alicyclic and aromatic) were used to cure resin and investigated how they influence on the performance, particularly thermal, electrochemical and mechanical properties. Thermal analysis confirmed that stability can be increased from 250 to 350 °C by examining the trend in T_{d10} . The stability and glass transition temperature (T_g) of the structures is in the following order: aromatic > alicyclic > linear. Throughout mechanical and electrochemical properties both were affected by structural difference of the matrix, although expected to date the increases in mechanical properties and the reduction of the trade-off between mechanical and electrochemical have not yet been examined.

1 INTRODUCTION

For many years now the automotive industry has been interested in a range of diverse activities, none more important than lightweight materials for improved safety and fuel efficiency. However, increasingly, greater demands are being placed on composite materials, to be not only structural but also functional. Whilst still in its infancy, the development of multifunctional composites, is becoming increasingly important academically and gaining attention from industry. Wetzel (2007) reported a multi-functional composite that has mechanical load bearing capability whilst also able to store electrochemical energy, known as a *structural composite battery (SCB)* [1]. More recently, Asp and Greenhalgh (2013) demonstrated SCB applications in automotive components, such as body panels, the car boot, doors and bonnet. The potential here is that energy efficiency can be improved by replacing heavy parts but also adding energy storage [2]. A SCB is similar in construction to a conventional battery in that it includes an electrolyte, electrodes (anode and cathode) and separator, and is fabricated via a layer by layer approach [1-4]. However, many technical challenges need to be overcome before SCB find their way into production vehicles.

In the view of solid electrolyte against the conventional electrolyte, the balance between the structural performance and ionic conductivity needs optimized which is often difficult because structural performance requires a rigid structure, while ionic conductivity needs sufficient molecular motion within the polyelectrolyte. Studies have explored ionic conductivity and mechanical properties through controlling experimental parameters, such as varying the concentration of lithium salts, cross-linking density, curing methods, inorganic filler and the plasticizer effect [5-9].

As our best knowledge, the aspect of the molecular structure difference of SPE for SCB has not been explored, yet. Moreover, there was not many studies on the electrochemical aspect for PEGDGE-based matrix. Thus, this study will show a further extension of applying different molecular structure in amine based curing agents on epoxy resin monomer and to confirm how they are affected on the characteristics of SPE which are applied as a structural composite battery in near future.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Poly (ethylene glycol) dicyclydyle ether (PEGDGE), triethylenetetraamine (TETA, $\geq 97.0\%$), 4,4'-methylenebis (cyclohexylamine) (MCHA), 4-aminophenyl sulfone (DDS, 97 %), propylene carbonate (PC, HPLC grade, 99.7%) and lithium trifluoromethanesulfonate (LiTf or lithium triflate) were obtained from Sigma Aldrich (Australia and USA). All chemicals were used as received. The epoxy resins used in this study were cured according to the general method described as below.

2.2 Techniques and Procedures

2.2.1 Solid Polyelectrolyte Preparation and Sample Fabrication

A series of SPE samples with different compositions were prepared. All samples including LiTf were prepared in a glovebox, under an argon atmosphere and dry conditions (<1 ppm H_2O , <1 ppm O_2), but pristine samples, which are without LiTf, were prepared in a fume hood as a purpose of examining the conversion of resin matrix. A stock solution of organic electrolyte including LiTf, denoted as *conductive source*, was prepared in a glove box due to the moisture sensitivity of lithium salts.

2.2.2 Thermal Analysis

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was performed using a TA Q200 in the cyclic method (heating-cooling-heating), with a heating and cooling rate both as $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, to determine glass transition temperature (T_g) changes by different chemical composition. Samples of 5–7 mg were placed inside an aluminum pan with a pinched lid and were inserted into a preheated oven before analysis, under a nitrogen atmosphere.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was used a TA Q50 in the isothermal method, with a heating rate $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, to confirm thermal stability. The weight samples for the measurements were used approximately 5 – 7 mg under a nitrogen atmosphere.

2.2.3 Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was performed in impedance testing mode with frequency range (1 MHz to 1 Hz) at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using a Gamry reference 600⁺. In addition, the EIS test via temperature changes was measured in a frequency range (1 kHz to 1 Hz) at $50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using a BCS-810 electrochemical workstation (Bio-Logic). As shown in figure 1, symmetric coin cells (lithium/lithium or stainless steel/stainless steel) and asymmetric coin cells (stainless steel/lithium) were assembled using CR 2032 coin cell, which is included pre-prepared film solid polyelectrolyte (SPE, diameter 12 mm and average thickness 800 μm), which is contained conductive source.

Figure 1. Different types of coin cell for electrochemical test; (a) uses for ionic conductivity of SPE and (b-c) for electrochemical stability.

To calculate the ionic conductivity of electrolyte, the equation, which has introduced on the previous studies [10-11], is used as follows;

$$\sigma = \frac{l}{R_b A}$$

σ : Ionic conductivity of electrolyte

R_b : Bulk resistance (the value can be acquired from impedance test)

A : Cross-sectional area of SPE sample

l : The length between electrodes (= thickness of SPE)

2.2.4 Mechanical Analysis

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) was performed using a TA Q800 in tension film mode. Bar shape film samples were clamped in the DMA with a length of 10 – 15 mm between the clamps. The starting temperature was set to 35 °C where it was held isothermally for 5 min. A fixed amplitude was applied as 15 μm and a single frequency used at 1 Hz for the measurements.

2.2.5 Fourier-Transform Infrared (FT-IR) Spectroscopy

FT-IR measurements were carried out with the precure sample mixture and on the cured SPE films to confirm the conversion of the resin. The measurements were performed using a Bruker Alpha FT-IR equipped with ATR (Attenuated total reflection) accessory unit, with a diamond ATR crystal. Samples were placed in the beam and measurements were made between 4000 and 400 cm^{-1} using an average of 64 scans with a resolution as 4 cm^{-1} .

2.2.6 X-ray Diffraction (XRD)

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed using a Malvern PANalytical X-pert powder with Cu $K\alpha$ radiation which is set a power setting as 40 kV and 30 mA. The SPE samples for XRD prepared as a powder and then they applied onto sticky part of Kapton tape prior to placing on a sample holder. The measurement was over the range of diffraction angle $2\theta = 10 - 60^\circ$, with a scan rate of 3.3 $^\circ \text{min}^{-1}$ at room temperature.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 System description

By many studies earlier, ethylene oxide (EO) units give rise to a high donor number for Li^+ and high chain flexibility, which are important to promote ion transport [12-13].

As shown in figure 2, the system used in the present study is based on the resin monomer including EO on the backbone and three different molecular structure in a curing agent. There were prepared two different resin systems including lithium triflate which is with/without organic electrolyte (propylene carbonate, PC). The conversion of polymer matrix was explored by the specific peak changes, particularly disappearance of epoxide ($-\text{O}-\text{C}-\text{O}-$) and amine ($\text{N}-\text{H}$) peaks as well as appearance of hydroxyl ($-\text{OH}$) peak, between precured and cured resin on FT-IR spectrogram.

Figure 2. A schematic diagram of PEG based resin based SPE matrixes, which cured by different curing agents in molecular structure including linear, alicyclic and aromatic.

3.2 FT-IR

The curing performance differs among the different composition of hardeners. Through the FT-IR in figure 3 (a-b), epoxide ($-\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}-$) and amine ($\text{N}-\text{H}$) bending, which is $850 - 915 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1580 - 1650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, are reduced after curing, but $-\text{OH}$ stretching peak, $3200 - 3550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, is appeared due to ring opening of epoxide group after curing with amine-based curing agent.

However, SPE cured by MCHA demonstrated a C-H stretching peak between $2840 - 3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ because of different molecular structure as an alicyclic in a curing agent.

Figure 3. FT-IR spectrogram for the conversion of PEGDGE-TETA (PEGDGE (T)) and PEGDGE-MCHA (PEGDGE (M)); (a-b) PEGDGE (T) and PEGDGE (M) IR spectrogram in range between 4,000 and 400 cm^{-1} (c) peak changes in detail by comparison between pre-cure and cured matrix.

According to the past literatures [18-19], hydrogen bonding investigated by the red and blue peak shifts which is -OH stretching ($3,600 - 3,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and -NH bending ($1,650-1,580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) respectively. As shown in figure 4 (b-c) and (e-f), the red and blue peak shifts from -OH stretching and -NH bending were investigated by increasing the concentration of conductive source in the matrix, and hence the concentration increment could be attributed hydrogen bonding with the hydroxyl groups.

Figure 4. FT-IR of PEGDGE (T) (a-c) and PEGDGE (M) (d-f); (a & d) full spectrum range of PEGDGE (T) and PEGDGE (M) matrix, (b-c) & (e-f) specific range between OH stretching / bending ($3,800$ and $3,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ / $1,450$ and $1,380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and -NH bending ($1,650$ and $1,580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) to investigate hydrogen bonding by changes of the concentration in conductive source.

In general, PEGDGE (T) and PEGDGE (M) both exhibited the OH stretching and bending peak intensity was increased by increasing the concentration of conductive source due to interaction

between resin matrix and lithium triflate ions. However, PEGDGE (T) with 0.6 and 1.2 wt % conductive source was interestingly observed decreasing peak intensity, and hence it might be interpreted due to the matrix nature depending on the ratio between ethylene oxide and lithium ion as shown on thermal stability above.

3.3 XRD

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was carried out to investigate whether lithium triflate is dissolved well in the resin matrix. In figure 5 (a) & (b), lithium triflate indicated the diffraction peaks between 10 and 50 °, but the pristine resin matrix, PEGDGE with TETA (PEGDGE (T)), showed a broad diffraction peak at around 18 ° due to the nature of cured epoxy resin as amorphous. However, the resin matrix including lithium triflate was also appeared the same diffraction peak trend as pristine resin, although the peak of lithium triflate is expected to reveal on the diffraction diagram.

Figure 5. XRD diffractogram of PEGDGE (T); (a) with organic electrolyte (propylene carbonate (PC) and (b) without PC.

According to the past studies [20-21], the disappearance of the peak of LiTf is reflected that it has been dissolved in the resin matrix, and hence it could be concluded that the different salt concentration from 0.6 to 1.8 wt % of conductive source is dissolved in the matrix.

3.4 Thermal performance of the SPE

As shown in figure 6 (a-b), all the resins showed relatively good thermal stability. The use of curing agents of different molecular structure to PEGDGE resin confirmed the increase in stability in the following order, aromatic > alicyclic > linear. In terms of the molecular structure, the aromatic ring is well known to be thermally and chemically stable structure because of its aromaticity, cyclic structure and electron deconjugation defined by good interaction between adjacent p-orbital, and the Huckel rule ($4n+2 \pi$ electrons in the conjugation system). Therefore, PEGDGE-DDS (PEGDGE (D)) exhibited better thermal stability than the other two, as well as confirmed relatively higher glass transition temperature (T_g) than the other matrixes as shown in figure 6 (d-f). However, DDS has a comparatively slower curing performance than the other two, although it has a good thermal and chemical resistance. Hence, PEGDGE (D) has not been conducted further on electrochemical and mechanical properties for this study, although the thermal analysis carried out to investigate the effect of molecular structure difference on thermal stability.

On the other hand, PEGDGE (M) in figure 6 (e) demonstrated a decreasing trend in T_g with increasing conductive source concentration because of the increasing chain flexibility afforded by its alicyclic structure.

Figure 6. TGA and DSC data for three different epoxy-amin based SPE; a) TGA of the resin matrix of PEGDGE with different curing agents used, b) TGA for showing thermal stability by increasing conductive source, (c) Derivative weight % of PEGDGE (T) and (M), (d-f) DSC results of PEGDGE matrix with three different curing agents used.

Throughout figure 6 (c), the investigation of resin thermal degradation was confirmed through the derivative weight loss peak and hence two degradation peaks on the PEGDGE (T) and PEGDGE (M) with 1.2 wt% conductive source found 320 / 390 °C and 290 / 378 °C, respectively. The first degradation peak was indicated around 10 wt% of weight loss, which is well-known as T_{d10} , and the rest of samples also showed the same degradation peak trend.

In figure 6 (b), the increasing concentration of conductive source, which is dissolved LiTf in propylene carbonate (PC) as mentioned earlier, in PEGDGE (M) and PEGDGE (D) presented the increment trend on thermal stability, but interestingly there was not shown the proportional increment of the thermal stability in PEGDGE (T) by increasing the concentration.

To clarify the thermal stability trend on PEGDGE (T) with conductive source, PEGDGE (T) including only lithium salts was prepared and characterised by TGA as shown in figure 7 (a). By comparing TGA trend between with/without solvent in the matrix, it could be confirmed that the thermal stability of PEGDGE (T) might be possibly dependent on the ratio between lithium salts and ethylene oxide rather than the concentration increment. By comparison of DSC data between figure 6 (d) and figure 7 (b), the use of PC in PEGDGE (T) was demonstrated playing a role in lowering T_g values than the samples without PC due to plasticizing effect of the organic electrolyte to the resin matrix.

Figure 7. TGA and DSC data for lithium salts directly into the resin matrix without solvent; (a) TGA with different [EO]: [Li] ratio (b) DSC with different [EO]: [Li] ratio.

3.5 Electrochemical and Mechanical performance of the SPE

To measure ionic conductivity of PEGDGE matrix used to cured curing agents in different molecular structure, the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) test, which evaluates the electrochemical characteristics of the coin cell by applying an AC potential at varying frequencies and measuring the current response of the cell, was examined. According to the previous study about EIS test, Nyquist plot shows the semicircle which can be defined the solid electrolyte interface (SEI) layer resistance at high-frequency and the charge transfer resistance at low-frequency [14-15].

Figure 8. Electrochemical analysis for PEGDGE (T) and PEGDGE (M) by a symmetric coin cell (SS/SPE/SS and Li/SPE/Li); A Nyquist plot (a-d); (a & d) PEGDGE (T) and PEGDGE (M) with different concentration of conductive source (0.6 and 1.8 wt%) and (b-c) PEGDGE (T) without organic electrolyte by different [EO]/[Li] ratio, (e) bode plot and (f) ionic conductivity of PEGDGE (T) and PEGDGE (M)

The trend of charge transfer resistance at low-frequency changes was investigated because resistance indicates whether a material can afford to flow of electric current. As points of view in the

concentration from figure 8 (a-d), the impedances showed a decrement trend by increasing conductive sources (LiTf + PC) or LiTf only, because increased ions in the matrix were affected on the trend.

The phase of SPE matrix at room temperature in figure 8 (c) is semi-crystalline and the segmental movement of the chains is not feasible to transport the Li ions [16], but the chain transfer resistance was decreased by increasing temperature due to the matrix phase change as amorphous. Therefore, it demonstrated that the matrix phase change was affected on ionic movement by changing temperature. However, the resistance revealed that the matrix cured with alicyclic molecules were higher than the matrix cured with aliphatic curing agent, and hence it could be assumed that Li ion transfer is affected by the molecular structure.

According to the previous study [17], the interfacial contact between electrode and electrolyte could be interpreted through bode and Nyquist plot. Bode plot in figure 8 (e) reveals additional contrasting conduction behavior of PEGDGE (T) and PEGDGE (M) and different slopes for the resin matrixes in the high frequency region showed that they differ ionic conduction behaviors due to their different compositions. Furthermore, PEGDGE (T)'s impedance value saturated at higher frequency range than PEGDGE (M) and it indicates that PEGDGE (T) presented in figure 8 (a) is mainly bulk resistance, while PEGDGE (M) includes both charge transfer resistance and bulk resistance. Hence, the interfacial contact to Li metal might be indicated higher on PEGDGE (T) than PEGDGE (M) due to supporting lower impedance data of PEGDGE (T) over all frequency range than PEGDGE (M) in figure 8 (a-b). Also, the statement above can be supported by the ionic conductivity of the matrix in figure 8 (f).

Figure 9. Mechanical properties of PEGDGE (T) and PEGDGE (M); (a) pictures of the sample collected, which is 20 mm in length and approximately 800 μm in thickness, right after curing (b) bar shape samples for mechanical properties by DMA (c) table for the results of the storage modulus at ambient temperature.

As shown in figure 9 (c), the storage modulus was decreased after the addition of conductive source and because the included solvent acted as a plasticizing effect. By comparison in figure 8 (a) and (d), increasing conductive source in the resin matrixes were shown decreasing trend in impedance, because the SPE matrix phase changed more amorphous by plasticizing effect and hence it was related to the trend of reduction on mechanical properties.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, PEGDGE matrix by curing with curing agents in different molecular structure was investigated. Clearly it has been shown that the molecular structure of the curing agent had a profound impact on the thermal stability, mechanical and electrochemical properties. Thermal analysis confirmed that stability can be increased from 250 to 350 °C by examining the trend in T_{d10} . The stability of the structures is in the following order: aromatic > alicyclic > linear. Throughout mechanical analysis, PEGDGE (T) and PEGDGE (M) both with conductive source were investigated relatively similar storage modulus as approximately 2 MPa. Moreover, the ionic conductivity of PEGDGE (T) and PEGDGE (M) at ambient temperature were 3.78×10^{-5} and 5.73×10^{-6} , respectively.

As a result, it was shown that mechanical and electrochemical properties both were affected by structural difference of the matrix, although expected to date the increases in mechanical properties and the reduction of the trade-off between mechanical and electrochemical have not yet been examined. This is the challenge ahead to increase chain flexibility through by reactive and non-reactive additives explore this relationship.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the Australian Research Council (ARC) Research Hub for Future Fibres (IH140100018) funded by the Australian Government for their financial support.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Asp and E. Greenhalgh, Structural power composite, *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 101, No. 12, 2014, pp. 41–61.
- [2] E. L. Wong, D. M. Baechle, K. Xu, R. H. Carter, J. F. Snyder, and E. D. Wetzel, Design and processing of structural composite batteries, *In: Proceedings Society for the Advancement of Materiel and Process Engineering (SAMPE)*, Baltimore, MD, USA, 2007.
- [3] N. Shirshova, H. Qian, M. S. P. Shaffer, J. H. G. Steinke, E. S. Greenhalgh, P. T. Curtis, and A. Bismarck, Structural composite supercapacitors, *Composites Part A*, Vol. 46, 2013, pp. 96–107
- [4] T. Carlson “*Multifunctional composite materials*”, Imperial College London PhD Thesis, 2013.
- [5] G. Lecayon, Y. Bouzimez, C. Le Gressus, C. Reynaud, C. Boiziau, C and C. Juret, Grafting and growing mechanisms of polymerised organic films onto metallic surfaces, *Chemical Physics Letters*, Vol. 91, 6, 1982, pp. 506–510.
- [6] S. Gabriel, R. Jérôme and C. Jérôme, Cathodic electrografting of acrylics: From fundamentals to functional coatings, *Progress in Polymer Science*, Vol. 35, 1, 2010, pp. 113–140.
- [7] P. Arora and Z. Zhang “Battery Separators” *Chemical Reviews*, Vol. 104, 10, 2004, pp. 4419–4462.
- [8] M. Willgert, M. Kjell and M. Johansson, Effect of Lithium Salt Content on the Performance of Thermoset Lithium Battery Electrolytes In Polymers for Energy Storage and Delivery: Polyelectrolytes for Batteries and Fuel Cells, *American Chemical Society*, 1096, 2012, pp. 4–55.
- [9] J. Snyder, E. Wetzel and C. Watson, Improving multifunctional behavior in structural electrolytes through copolymerization of structure- and conductivity-promoting monomers, *Polymer*, Vol. 50, 20, 2009, pp. 4906–4916.
- [10] M. Watanabe, M. Togo, K. Sanui, N. Ogata, T. Kobayashi and Z. Ohtaki, Ionic conductivity of polymer complexes formed by poly(β -propiolactone) and lithium perchlorate, *Macromolecules*, Vol. 17, 12, 1984, pp.2908–2912.
- [11] M. Echeverri, C. Hamad and T. Kyu, Highly conductive, completely amorphous polymer electrolyte membranes fabricated through photo-polymerization of poly (ethylene glycol diacrylate) in mixtures of solid plasticizer and lithium salt, *Solid State Ionics*, Vol. 254, 2014, pp.92–100.
- [12] Z. Xue, D. He and X. Xie, Poly (ethylene oxide)-based electrolytes for lithium-ion batteries, *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*, Vol. 3, 38, 2015, pp.19218–19253.
- [13] Z. Gadjourova, Y. Andreev, D. Tunstall and P. Bruce, Ionic conductivity in crystalline polymer electrolytes, *Nature*, Vol. 412, 6846, 2001, pp. 520–523.
- [14] M. Ryou, D. Lee, J. Lee, Y. Lee, J. Park and J. Choi, Excellent Cycle Life of Lithium-Metal Anodes in Lithium-Ion Batteries with Mussel-Inspired Polydopamine-Coated Separators, *Advanced Energy Materials*, Vol. 2, 6, 2012, pp. 645–650.

- [15] M. Ryou, Y. Lee, Y. Lee, M. Winter and P. Bieker, Mechanical Surface Modification of Lithium Metal: Towards Improved Li Metal Anode Performance by Directed Li Plating, *Advanced Functional Materials*, Vol. 25, 6, 2015, pp. 834–841.
- [16] F. Peters, F. Langer, N. Hillen, K. Koschek, I. Bardenhagen, J. Schwenzel, and M. Busse, M, Correlation of Mechanical and Electrical Behavior of Polyethylene Oxide-Based Solid Electrolytes for All-Solid State Lithium-Ion Batteries, *Batteries*, Vol.5, 1, 2019, 26.
- [17] H. Lim, H. Lim, X. Xing, B. Lee, H. Liu, C. Coaty, H. Kim and P. Liu, Solid Electrolyte Layers by Solution Deposition, *Advanced Materials Interfaces*, Vol. 5, 8, 2018, 1701328.
- [18] F. Peters, F. Langer, N. Hillen, K. Koschek, I. Bardenhagen, J. Schwenzel and M. Busse, M, Correlation of Mechanical and Electrical Behavior of Polyethylene Oxide-Based Solid Electrolytes for All-Solid State Lithium-Ion Batteries, *Batteries*, Vol. 5, 1, 2018, 26.
- [19] S. Roy, T. Jansen and J. Knoester, Structural classification of the amide I sites of a β -hairpin with isotope label 2DIR spectroscopy, *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, Vol. 12, 32, 2010, pp. 9347–9357.
- [20] S. Chhetri, P. Suneel, N. Murmu, S. Srivastava and T. Kulia, Electromagnetic interference shielding and thermal properties of non-covalently functionalized reduced graphene oxide/epoxy composites, *AIMS Materials Science*, Vol. 4, 1, 2017, pp. 61–74.
- [21] S. Sun, L. Zheng, L. Yuan, Q. Guan, G. Liang and A. Gu, Multifunctional epoxy resin/polyacrylonitrile-lithium trifluoromethanesulfonate composites films with very high transparency, high dielectric permittivity, breakdown strength and mechanical properties, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, Vol. 134. 34, 2017, 45218.